

The Australian 3D Resistivity Model 2026

Discussion paper June 2022

Vision: Completing the Australian Lithospheric Architecture Magnetotelluric Project by 2026

Background: The primary mission of the Australian Lithospheric Architecture Magnetotelluric Project (AusLAMP), commencing in 2013, has been to generate a 3D electrical resistivity model of the continental lithosphere from 3000 long-period MT sites spaced approximately 50 km. The models, and their interpretations, are of value to:

- The international geoscience research community to understand the fundamental tectonic evolution of the Australian continent.
- Geoscience Australia, State and Territory Geological Surveys as pre-competitive data and models.
- Resources industries to define regional-scale prospectivity.
- Space-weather agencies in natural hazard mapping of Geomagnetically Induced Currents (GIC).

Progress: Since 2013 about 1400 sites have been funded and collected by multiple agencies including AuScope, Geoscience Australia and all State and Territory Geological Surveys. To date, South Australia, New South Wales, Victoria and Tasmania have been completed, most of the Northern Territory and smaller parts of Queensland and Western Australia. However, in recent years the program has slowed through a combination of covid restrictions on travel, increased costs and issues of access. The influence of the UNCOVER agenda has also softened in the last few years with the new demand for critical minerals.

Pathways to completion: Completion of the AusLAMP array with the current density of sites at the same rate will take at least another decade. However, with site costs of \$10,000 for very remote locations and issues of access, it is unlikely to continue at the same rate as the last decade, and the total cost for the remaining 1600 sites would thus be a minimum \$16 million.

Proposal: A pragmatic approach to complete the AusLAMP array in a reasonable time and cost is to reduce the site spacing from about 50 km to 100 km, as shown in the figure for remaining sites. The reduction in density loses some fidelity but completes national continental coverage and provides context for higher spatial density infill grids. The logistics would then be:

- 380 sites to complete (mostly in WA and Qld).
- For a site cost of \$10,000 the total completion program would be \$4 million.
- 100 sites per year could be collected using AuScope and GA long-period MT instruments.
- Project would be undertaken from 2023-2026.

Outputs and Outcomes:

- Time series data for every site will be made available through AuScope portal.
- MT responses will be available for every site.
- Nested and numerical models at craton and orogen scales will be made publicly available.
- Regional-scale prospectivity maps produced for the resources industry.
- GIC hazard maps will be produced for space weather agencies, power grids and utilities industries.